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THE IMPACT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE ON SELF EFFICACY OF HEALTH STAFF IN JAMMU AND KASHMIR

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Abstract

This paper attempts to identify the impact of emotional intelligence on self efficacy of Health staff in the state of Jammu and Kashmir. As a fairly new concept, emotional intelligence has only been discussed for the past twenty years and valid researches on the effects of emotional intelligence in the work environment are still rare. This paper tries to add to the discussion with an analysis of the links between emotional intelligence and self efficacy. The method of linear regression is used to fulfill the above mentioned task, the results of this peculiar study, highlight a significantly positive relation, among the constructs considered.

Key Word: Emotional Intelligence, Self Efficacy, Health

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Introduction:

In the past few decades, emotional intelligence has emerged one of the hotly debated topics in behavioral science gaining attention of researchers and practitioners alike (Jeffery, 2005). Radha, (2008) expressed that emotional intelligence has come to occupy an imperative position practically in all areas of human functioning. Palmer, Donaldson, and Stough (2002) found that higher emotional intelligence was a predictor of life satisfaction. Additionally, Pellitteri (2002) reported that people higher in emotional intelligence were also more likely to use an adaptive defense style and thus exhibited healthier psychological adaptation. Performance measures of emotional intelligence have illustrated that higher levels of E.I. are associated with an increased likelihood of attending to health and appearance, positive

interactions with friends and family, and owning objects that are reminders of their loved ones (Brackett, Mayer, & Warner, in press). Emotional Intelligence holds significance as it deals with the cognitive aspects of life.

Emotional intelligence is defined as, one's tendency to recognize, evaluate and handle emotional state of his own and others' as well, therefore be able to use this information to accomplish certain objectives. (Choudary, 2010). Similarly Stone *et al* (1998) stated that EI is the ability to empathize, persevere, control impulses, communicate clearly, make thoughtful decisions, solve problems, and work with others in a way that earns friends and success. Another definition designates EI as the ability to utilize the emotional condition of an individual, group or own-self to achieve a certain goal or a set of goals or objectives (Fox & Spector, 2000). This concept could be pointed out, as the ability to appreciate the emotions and identify the likely outcomes of them and finally via this knowledge, the individual or a group control others and attain goals (Prati, Douglas, Ferris, Ammeter, & Buckley, 2003). There are a number of studies conducted all over the world featuring emotional intelligence, Kavousy, Ardahaey, & Chivaei, (2007) observe, a direct relation between degree of emotional control and sensibility towards utilizing time in an individual. This relationship is also significant with other dimensions of emotional intelligence such as self monitoring and regulation. In another similar work, the feminine functional managers are found to be more emotionally stable, in comparison with their masculine counterparts. The exposure to the business environment, norms and values also facilitate an individual to develop this particular ability. (Kaifi & Noori, 2010). Now we turn our focus, towards academia, where, Madhar, (2010) notes, that, the emotionally sound lecturers are really a source of inspiration for the pupils, to be effective learners. The teacher should be able to tolerate difficult and somewhat ambitious questions, from the students and also should be able to provide relevant and satisfactory answers, to facilitate learning among the students. In the literature relevant to leadership, this construct is not neglected, because of its profound role, herefore, Guillen, (2011), points, that emotional intelligence plays an important role in the

recognition of the leader among people, because the leader faces the insulting behavior of others in the introductory stage of his or her career, thus placing a premium on EI of leaders, which becomes an essential for forging through immense resistance for the leaders, Doaei, Alizadeh, & Tabrizi, (2010), this team of well known scholars, made an addition, that, the emotional strength of a person plays an invincible role in gaining the authority on the basis of knowledge in an organization, because a person faces the challenge of, admitting a reasonable level of knowledge, so that it should not threaten the people who have the authority currently, another facet of emotional sensibility in leadership is, leaders' ability to avoid negative thinking, biasness and they also give sacrifices and understanding others' behavior to accomplish the goals of the team. These abilities are imperative for effectively successful teams. (Prati, Douglas, Ferris, Ammeter, & Buckley, 2003) Webb, (2011) comes, with his own version of this variable, and says, the emotionally strong top managers have an imperative role in inspiring the employees, to be more productive, and increasing their job and organizational attachment as well. This observation emphasizes on the decentralization of authority, job autonomy and flexible timing, and it also has a clue for corporate level managers to increase, the interaction, with their subordinates, in the organizations, spread across different walks of life. The role of the staff with higher level of emotional control is undeniable, in increasing devotion towards the company, because they give time to the management to solve job related problems, they do not get frustrated due to long hours of work and are found contented with the pay level as well, thus supporting the company to prosper in the marketplace (Moradi & Ardahaey, 2011). The impact of emotional control is also a crucial factor in the performance, of teams in various sorts of organizations, members of successful teams are careful, in expressing their emotions and are coordinative, forthcoming and supportive, are also sensitive towards, others' feelings as well. (Prati, Douglas, Ferris, Ammeter, & Buckley, 2003), Lopes, Grewal, Kadis, Gall, & Salovey, (2006) also came across, the strong link between job performance and emotional intelligence, but it is to be noted here that, EI also entails, the ability to demonstrate an emotion, which is

appropriate according to the situation, another interesting note is shared, by Jordan, Ashkanasy, & Harter, (2002), that, the staff with low EQ, is more prone to the pressures imposed by, uncertainty on the job for example threat of getting fired, but their counterparts with higher EQ are less affected by this situation, the former group engage themselves in negative work behavior often. Donaldson-Feilder & Bond, (2004), mentioned a non significant relation between EI, fitness and safety of the worker, such as cognitive soundness and physical health, therefore the companies should avoid, deploying resources to enhance this relation and Kernbach & Schutte, (2005) report a positive relation between, the EI of salesperson and buyer content with the delivery of product, whenever, the transfer of product from supplier to buyer is relatively simple, this relationship enhances manifolds, but decreases slightly, if it is other way around. Now this study fixes, the spot light on more relevant work, where, McQueen, (2004) suggests, that the medical staff is often found to be emotionally attached with the patients under care in a medical facility, but this concept is neglected, during training, on the other hand.

Self Efficacy Juárez & Contreras, (2008), define self efficacy as one's determination to face various challenges, difficulties and conditions in life. On the other side, (Gist & Mitcell), (1992), mentioned it as, one's belief, to get the things right regarding a particular job, this concept depends upon the various other factors, such as the qualification, competency, ability and experience of an individual under consideration. The important facet identified here is self confidence of an individual to overcome a certain challenges or obstacles. The factors, which cause, the self efficacy of an individual to flourish are, 1) Mastery Experiences, which entail, a person's exposure to the situation, in which he or she was able to learn a peculiar skill or task, proficiently and as well as quickly. 2) Vicarious Experiences come from noticing others, with similar personality dimensions, succeeding in a certain field. 3) Social Persuasion, it refers to the peers, friends and colleagues' collective effort to convince, an individual, that he or she has an adequate

potential, to perform these tasks. (Bandura, Self Efficacy in Changing Societies, 1995)

Now, we study, the concept of self efficacy, in relation to other constructs, such as, there is a significantly positive link, discovered between the belief of a person, that he could resolve a particular interpersonal dispute and his actions to pursue the matter proactively, thus attempting to uproot the cause of the disturbance, to nullify the possibility of serious ramifications. (Eizen & Desivilya, 2005), this concept under consideration, has a close relation with entrepreneurship, because, often successful entrepreneurs, tend to be uncomfortable with their work in some organization and them, therefore search for greater challenges in their lives. The major motivating factor is their self belief, that they could run their own business more successfully. Thus this vary belief compels them to start a new venture. (Wong, Lee, & Leung, 2006) Freudenberg, Cameron, & Brimble, (2010), identify the role of self perception in enhancing the ability of graduate students to enhance, their academic achievements, teachers and administration in academia, should work and support, students to increase their self belief and confidence, because these factors, have an immense impact on their performance. (Saleem & Shah), 2011, believe, that, self confidence has an impact of reducing the work related tension in teaching practices, because in this case the individual takes pride in his or her work and readily willing to manage, the physical and as well as mental pressures associated with the profession. Bandura, Barbaranelli, Caprara, & Pastorelli, (2001), observe, that self concept plays an imperative role, when individuals choose their occupational paths and the academic performance becomes somewhat irrelevant in this regard, because adolescents do not consider this factor while making an occupational choice. There is a strong connection between, the level of efficacy and the will to quit unhealthy and non hygienic practices (Strecher, DeVellis, Becker, & Rosenstock, 1986), so it is imperative for rehabilitation physicians, to increase, the efficacy content, in the patient to facilitate recovery, the other study on the topic of managing, work stress, depicts, that, an individual should recuperate from the psychological stress caused by the failure at the

office, as soon as possible, this could be accomplished, through emotional self efficacy and emotional sensibility (Sonnetag & Krue, 2006), these traits, would facilitate, the employee, to cope with upcoming problems, at another point of time, the medical staff, going through training, with heightened self motivation and belief, are found to be performing adequately well in their objective structured clinical exams. (Mavis, 2001). Now on, the spot light is focused, on the area of interest that is, the degree of interaction among emotional intelligence and self efficacy in Jammu and Kashmir among health staff, one research in this domain points out, the significantly direct relationship, among the self belief and emotional control of health staff working in hospitals, and the intensity of self efficacy and emotional intelligence rose, with the rise in age and exposure to frequent challenging tasks (Bryan, 2007), Another relevant study, reported, that the candidates opting for nursing as profession at entry test, with greater degree of professional self-reliance, are believed, to have better probability of getting good to excellent scores in the exam mentioned above (McLaughlin, Moutray, & Muldoon, 2007). As the above review of the studies, advocates, for the significantly positive relation, between EI and other relevant constructs, such as job performance, time management and so on. Similar relations, with self efficacy are observed, throughout the previous section, for example, choice of conflict management strategies and entrepreneurship and so forth. For instance Elfenbein (2006) believes that accurate perception of individuals' emotions (type and intensity of emotions) facilitate prediction and perception of future performances. Given to the above findings about importance of emotional intelligence and self-efficacy and role of these variables on individuals' success the present survey has been conducted to provide evidences regarding the impact of emotional intelligence on health staffs self-efficacy beliefs in hospitals of Jammu and Kashmir.

METHODOLOGY

Objective of the present survey is to study and perceive impact degree of emotional intelligence on self-efficacy of health staff in Jammu and Kashmir Hospitals to determine which dimensions of emotional intelligence affect employees' self-efficacy and how much is the portion of each one in self-efficacy. This survey is applied in terms of purpose, descriptive-correlation in terms of data collection and is based on structural equations modeling. Structural equations model is a comprehensive statistical approach to test hypotheses about relations among observed variables and latent variables. It is possible to test acceptability of theoretical models in special populations and since most existing variables in psychological and managerial surveys are in latent form necessity of using such models becomes more increasingly (Segares, 1997). The present survey has been conducted on employees of various hospitals in jammu and Kashmir.

Given to research literature in the previous section the illustrated model in figures (1) and (2) constructs the substructure of the present survey. Self-efficacy variable has ten self-efficacy questions that the obtained high scores show high self-efficacy. About emotional intelligence structure the intended dimensions are tested to study their relationship with self-efficacy.

Given to above issues the following hypotheses have been represented to be studied and tested:

H1: emotional intelligence affects employees' self-efficacy.

H2: self-awareness affects staffs self-efficacy.

H3: self-regulation affects staffs self-efficacy.

H4: self-motivation affects staffs self-efficacy.

H5: sympathy affects staffs self-efficacy.

H6: social skills affect staffs self-efficacy.

GFI, AGFI, NNFI (TLI), NFI, CFI and IFI. Given to these indexes a model has suitable goodness in which χ^2 with regard to degree of freedom (df) is less than 3; amount of RMSEA is less than 10%; amounts of GFI, AGFI, NNFI (TLI), NFI, CFI and IFI are more than 90% and amount of PNFI is more than 50%.

RESULTS

Structural equations modeling method was used to study total goodness of the conceptual model. Testing hypotheses of both models was conducted using Amos software. The first model measures the impact of emotional intelligence on

self-efficacy and the second model measures the impact of each dimension of emotional intelligence on self-efficacy. First all measurement models must be analyzed separately in order to determine indexes are

acceptable to what extent for these models. Thus five measurement models that are related to variables are tested separately. Total goodness indexes for measurement models have been illustrated in table (2).

Table 1- Total indexes of measurement models

Indices Name	χ^2/df	GFI	AGFI	NNFI	NFI	CFI	IFI	PNFI	RMSEA
self-efficacy	2.52	0.914	0.946	0.933	0.906	0.962	0.925	0.643	0.070
self-awareness	2.34	0.916	0.932	0.918	0.923	0.919	0.963	0.762	0.041
self-regulation	2.62	0.955	0.914	0.925	0.928	0.973	0.987	0.603	0.037
self-motivation	1.80	0.956	0.918	0.943	0.946	0.914	0.964	0.844	0.027
Sympathy	2.35	0.920	0.975	0.938	0.966	0.907	0.927	0.772	0.001
social skills	2.20	0.914	0.933	0.972	0.911	0.928	0.903	0.665	0.051
Recommended Value	3 >	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %50	< 10%

Analysis of the above table concluded that measurement models have suitable results and in other words total indexes confirm this issue that data supports the model well. After studying and confirming measurement models

in the first step, path analysis is used in the second step to test hypotheses. Total indexes of path analysis for two conceptual models are represented in tables (2) and (3).

Table 2- Total indexes of the primary conceptual model of the survey

Indices Name	χ^2 / df	GFI	AGFI	NNFI	NFI	CFI	IFI	PNFI	RMSEA
Final model1	2.71	0.903	0.953	0.971	0.946	0.917	0.971	0.631	0.053
Recommended value	3 >	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %50	< 10%

Table 3- Total indexes of the secondary conceptual model of the survey

Indices Name	χ^2 / df	GFI	AGFI	NNFI	NFI	CFI	IFI	PNFI	RMSEA
Final model2	1.55	0.974	0.947	0.966	0.978	0.907	0.913	0.667	0.049
Recommended value	3 >	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %90	> %50	< 10%

Given to the above issues it could be concluded that total indexes reveal suitable goodness of the model by data. In other words we can say that the collected data supports the model well.

Structural equations model of the two conceptual models along with regression coefficients are represented in figures (3) and (4).

Two partial indexes of critical amount and P amount are used to test hypotheses' significance after studying and confirming the model. Critical amount is obtained through dividing "the estimated regression weight" by "the standard error" which must be more than 1.96 based on significance level 0.05 and if it is less than this amount, the related parameter is not important

in the model. Also amounts less than 0.05 for P show significant difference of the calculated amount for regression weights equal to zero at confidence level 95%. Hypotheses, regression coefficients and amounts of partial indexes related to each hypothesis are represented in table (3).

Table 4- regression coefficients and results of hypotheses testing

Hypothesis	Variable	Variable	Estimate	C	R
H 1	Emotional intelligence	Self-Efficacy	0 . 6 9	6 . 8 3	
H 2	Self-awareness	Self-Efficacy	0 . 8 2	8 . 3 2	
H 3	Self-regulation	Self-Efficacy	0 . 5 4	5 . 2 6	
H 4	Self-motivation	Self-Efficacy	0 . 6 9	6 . 9 8	
H 5	S y m p a t h y	Self-Efficacy	0 . 5 0	5 . 0 5	
H 6	S o c i a l s k i l l s	Self-Efficacy	0 . 6 1	6 . 0 9	

Results given in table (4) confirmed all hypotheses with 95% confidence

DISCUSSION

Self-efficacy theory that was proposed by Bandura in 1997 revealed that it wasn't a temporary concept. Researches of the two recent decades highlight importance of self-efficacy in individuals' success. Therefore, determining predicting factors of self-efficacy is so valuable. Objective of the present survey has been to study the impacts of emotional intelligence as predicting factors of employees' self-efficacy at Isfahan University. Results of hypotheses testing demonstrate that emotional intelligence and all its four dimensions have a significant impact on employees' self-efficacy. Standard coefficient of causal relationship between emotional intelligence and self-efficacy of employees is equal to 65% which shows emotional intelligence has a high capability to predict self-efficacy. This confirms results of previous theories and researches regarding effectiveness of emotional intelligence on self-efficacy (Moir and Oliver 2008, Rastegar and Memarpour 2009, Moafian and Ghanizade 2009, Rathi and Rastuji 2008). Research evidences indicate failure in emotions management (increased anxiety and inefficient stress) is often the direct result of believing in low self-efficacy (Bandura 1997, Salovey and Mayer 2002). Those who have no confidence in their capabilities will get disappointed under risky conditions and the possibility to act effectively is decreased. Such individuals fear to encounter with challenging issues and thus their performance is damaged which would be led to more sense of inefficiency (Maddux, 1995). On the other side, high anxiety decreases

performance and consequently sense of self-efficacy is reduced. Therefore, an individual who has a high emotional intelligence would control his feelings if necessary and deals with issues desirably. In explaining the relationship between emotional intelligence and self-efficacy it must be stated that individuals who can perceive and regulate their emotions and that of others could create stronger social support networks and would have a higher sense of empowerment given that emotional intelligence includes a set of inter-related skills to perceive assessment and expression of emotions precisely, have access to emotions or create them for emotional and rational growth (Mayer and Salovey, 1997) and that self-efficacy beliefs affect manner of thinking, how to deal with emotional health problems, decision-making and confronting with stress and depression (Bandura and Locke, 2003). In contrast, those who have low emotional intelligence don't have the recognition ability and compatibility with others' emotions that are necessary for interpersonal relationships (Ciarrochi, 2001). Both constructs are a set of skills, talents and capabilities which enhance the individual's ability to be successful in confronting with environmental pressures and necessities. Accordingly, both variables have a positive relationship and could predict each other. Generally, it must be stated that emotional intelligence has an important role in fostering self-efficacy beliefs and positive self-concept among medical staff and given that it is relatively fixed unlike intelligence quotient it is possible to enhance emotional intelligence through education. By growing emotional

intelligence of employees they obtain necessary interpersonal skills and are converted into knowledgeable employees and such positive changes enable them to be productive and efficient, enhance their skills, be satisfied with their function and obtain more successes. Therefore it is necessary to hold educational workshops for instructors and those involved in medical to be trained and become familiar with the importance of such variables using appropriate strategies and models.

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